

Free bonding energy between cations of Entisols, Inceptisols and Alfisols of India

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Manuscript received 27 June 2000, revised 24 July 2001, accepted 12 November 2001

One hundred twenty surface soil samples have been collected from two locations, viz. districts of Surguja and Raigarh, representing soils of order, Entisols, Inceptisols and Alfisols, to evaluate the free bonding energy (ΔG_r) between cations of the corresponding soils of North-Eastern part of Central India. The cation exchange capacity is higher in the Alfisols of both the sites, followed by the Inceptisols and the Entisols studied. The free bonding energy between K and Ca in Entisols and Inceptisols is found positive in both the areas showing ready availability of K over Ca and Na. In general, the ΔG_r values for Na-Ca exchange in Entisols of both the study areas are found to be positive, which indicates that these soils also release more Na^+ than Ca^{2+} . Inceptisols and Alfisols of both the areas are characterized by the negative values of free bonding energy for Na-Ca and Ca-Mg exchange, which indicates that these soils release more Ca^{2+} compared to Na^+ , while the negative ΔG_r values for Ca-Mg exchange suggest that these soils prefer Ca^{2+} , thereby releasing Mg^{2+} ion under favorable conditions. Due to the more Mg^{2+} in the soil solution of Alfisols of the study area, these soils would pose more water-logging problem, if irrigated unjudiciously, since Mg is known to have similar effect like Na to create water-logging problem in the soils.

In soil system where a good number of exchangeable cations are present, the change in free bonding energy between K-Ca, K-Na, Ca-Mg and Na-Ca provides valuable information on the availability of Ca^{2+} , Mg^{2+} , K^+ and Na^+ availability in soil solution because of the fact that the free bonding energy is a single value constant of the thermodynamic state of the system and is an extensive property. In a system consisting of compositionally variable minerals free energy has greatly contributed to the exchange complex¹. Free bonding energy between cations is a tool to assess the releasing pattern of cations in a soil system. The present study was thus undertaken to assess the complex behavior of the soils in the release of various cations in the North-Eastern part of Madhya Pradesh.

Results and Discussion

All the soils, viz. Entisols, Inceptisols and Alfisols were sandy loam, sandy clay loam, clay loam and clay in texture and showed neither salinity nor alkalinity problem. In general, the soils were found to be neutral to slightly acidic in reaction, with pH ranging between 6.0 and 7.6, with a mean value of 6.8 in the district of Surguja and 5.8, and 7.6 with a mean value of 6.4 in the district of Raigarh. Entisols and Alfisols in Location-1 and Entisols and Inceptisols in Location-2 required lime application for optimum crop production to maintain neutral pH of the soils. In general, the organic carbon was recorded low in soils of both the sites,

that ranged from 0.26–0.64 and 0.38–0.84% with an average values of 0.48 and 0.58% in Surguja and Raigarh districts, respectively. Free CaCO_3 was absent in all the soils except Alfisols of the district of Raigarh. These findings agree with the views that, due to comparatively higher precipitation, the bases leached to a greater depth and ensured the absence of calcium carbonate in upper layer of the soils; similar reports are available from earlier study² for the soils of the Eastern Madhya Pradesh.

Free bonding energy (ΔG_r) between cations :

The values of free bonding energy (ΔG_r) (Table 1) revealed that ΔG_r values for K-Ca and K-Na exchange in Entisols were positive and ranged 2.02–8.22 and 0.00–7.48 kJ mol^{-1} , respectively, in Location-1 while 4.67–9.10 and 3.38–8.13 kJ mol^{-1} in Location-2. In Inceptisols of both the locations, these values were recorded positive in the range 0.01–4.46 and 0.00–13.87 kJ mol^{-1} , respectively, in Location-1, whereas in Location-2 the ΔG_r for K-Ca and K-Na exchange were 0.16–3.71 and 5.62–12.09 kJ mol^{-1} , respectively. Higher positive values of ΔG_r in both the locations were observed for the Entisols. The positive values of ΔG_r between K-Ca and K-Na exchange in Entisols and Inceptisols suggested ready availability of K over Ca and Na with the soils preferring Ca^{2+} and Na^+ ions on exchange sites and K^+ ions in soil solution. Thus, these soils were unlikely to pose any sodium hazard³. The black soils of

Note

Table 1. Free bonding energy (ΔG_f , kJ mol⁻¹) of cations of the soils of Eastern Madhya Pradesh

Location	Sample no.	Entisols				Inceptisols				Alfisols			
		K-Ca	K-Na	Na-Ca	Ca-Mg	K-Ca	K-Na	Na-Ca	Ca-Mg	K-Ca	K-Na	Na-Ca	Ca-Mg
Location-1 : District – Surguja (Eastern Madhya Pradesh)													
Sitapur	1	7.21	4.73	2.48	-0.81	0.79	10.96	-11.76	-0.98	-3.51	7.70	-11.21	-0.45
	2	4.52	3.98	0.54	-0.49	0.01	9.62	-9.61	-0.97	-2.3	8.57	-11.57	-0.45
	3	6.77	5.85	0.92	1.52	1.65	8.26	-3.25	-0.67	-0.93	9.18	-10.11	-1.83
	4	8.04	5.32	-1.09	0.30	1.16	7.26	-2.82	-1.81	-0.99	9.10	-11.18	-0.51
	5	2.02	1.16	0.85	-0.20	1.19	7.48	-7.53	1.20	-0.85	10.61	-11.47	-1.08
	mean	5.71	4.21	0.74	-0.30	1.00	8.72	-6.99	-1.13	-1.72	9.03	-11.11	-0.86
Ambikapur	1	5.14	5.90	-0.75	0.11	4.45	9.87	-5.43	-0.96	-0.52	8.02	-8.53	-0.37
	2	5.14	-	-	0.88	3.48	-	-	-1.41	1.38	7.84	-6.18	-2.55
	3	6.90	5.80	1.09	1.42	0.58	9.47	-8.92	-1.05	0.20	6.39	-6.19	-1.61
	4	6.31	5.50	0.81	1.09	2.18	11.65	-9.46	-0.96	-1.95	8.45	-10.40	-0.57
	5	3.90	4.70	-0.55	1.57	0.61	9.96	-9.35	-1.19	0.27	10.29	-10.01	-0.62
	mean	5.48	5.48	0.15	1.00	2.26	10.24	-8.29	-1.11	-0.12	8.20	-8.26	-1.14
Surajpur	1	5.50	7.48	2.01	0.12	0.52	7.74	-8.26	-1.78	1.05	8.87	-7.82	-2.39
	2	5.61	-	-	0.43	3.16	7.75	-4.59	-2.68	0.12	7.01	-7.36	-2.00
	3	6.00	6.92	-0.92	1.69	4.44	10.29	-5.85	-1.49	-0.69	8.25	-8.94	-2.68
	4	7.61	5.53	1.29	2.17	2.30	-	-	-0.8	-2.19	7.01	-9.2	-1.77
	5	5.61	6.22	-0.61	0.15	1.59	9.49	-7.89	-1.48	-2.16	7.23	-9.2	-0.72
	mean	6.07	6.54	0.44	0.91	2.40	8.82	-6.65	-1.65	-0.77	7.67	-8.50	-1.91
Balrampur	1	3.04	-	-	-0.57	1.68	10.72	-9.04	-1.36	-1.44	5.29	-6.73	-5.86
	2	4.86	5.82	-0.96	0.05	2.90	10.44	-7.78	-1.09	-1.99	6.5	-7.69	-0.8
	3	6.75	-	-	-0.31	4.23	11.85	-8.10	-1.38	0.47	9.54	-9.07	-2.26
	4	6.69	6.86	-0.19	0.62	2.38	12.48	-10.09	-1.32	-1.05	8.3	-4.72	-1.43
	5	8.22	-	-	-0.5	2.24	13.87	-11.53	-1.72	-0.99	8.45	-9.44	-1.03
	mean	5.91	6.34	-0.58	-0.14	2.69	11.87	-9.31	-1.37	-1.00	7.62	-7.53	-2.28
Over all mean		5.79	5.45	0.33	0.37	2.14	9.95	-7.85	-1.32	-0.90	8.13	-8.85	-1.55
Location-2 : District – Raigarh (Eastern Madhya Pradesh)													
Sarangarh	1	5.91	5.22	0.69	-1.07	1.78	8.58	-6.81	-0.54	-1.61	6.31	-7.92	-0.47
	2	7.32	7.41	-0.09	-1.75	0.70	8.37	-7.66	-0.74	-2.18	6.93	-7.99	-1.04
	3	5.35	6.15	-0.80	-0.91	2.75	9.67	-6.92	-1.67	-2.18	4.97	-7.14	-2.95
	4	8.10	5.75	2.35	-2.03	0.58	6.72	-6.14	-2.43	-0.39	5.84	-6.23	-3.56
	5	8.05	3.38	4.68	-0.49	0.16	7.83	-7.67	-2.07	-2.02	5.30	-7.32	-1.77
	mean	6.95	5.58	1.37	-1.25	1.19	8.23	-7.04	-1.49	-1.68	5.87	-7.32	-1.96
Raigarh	1	6.48	7.72	-1.24	-1.37	3.64	12.09	-8.44	-1.28	0.32	6.88	-6.57	-2.30
	2	7.73	6.86	0.47	-2.32	2.82	11.70	-8.65	-2.50	-1.40	7.28	-8.69	-2.67
	3	9.10	5.60	-2.21	-1.86	0.57	8.67	-8.11	-0.18	-1.31	7.70	-8.30	-2.43
	4	6.33	6.31	0.02	0.27	2.58	10.13	-6.67	-1.48	0.19	7.29	-7.09	-2.65
	5	4.67	3.92	0.75	-1.72	0.76	7.17	-6.40	-2.52	-0.20	8.06	-8.27	-3.15
	mean	6.86	6.08	-0.44	-1.40	2.07	9.95	-7.65	-1.59	-0.48	7.44	-7.78	-2.64
Baramkela	1	7.83	5.99	1.83	-2.14	1.25	5.62	-5.82	-2.69	-1.54	7.91	-9.45	-2.68
	2	8.22	7.44	0.78	-2.42	2.22	8.21	-6.44	-3.03	-1.90	7.52	-9.43	-2.76
	3	8.92	7.62	1.30	-2.62	3.55	10.77	-7.22	-2.89	-2.20	6.61	-8.81	-2.46
	4	6.90	8.13	-1.23	-0.94	0.88	10.37	-9.49	-2.16	-0.70	8.15	-10.97	-2.43
	5	5.88	6.06	-0.18	0.79	1.55	7.88	-6.33	-1.70	0.27	7.41	-7.15	-3.25
	mean	7.55	7.05	0.50	-1.47	1.89	8.57	-7.06	-2.49	-1.21	7.52	-9.16	-2.72
Gharghoda	1	7.40	4.10	3.30	-1.91	3.27	9.60	-6.33	-2.28	1.50	6.78	-5.28	-1.62
	2	8.58	5.15	3.43	-1.44	3.69	9.87	-6.18	-3.40	1.42	6.80	-5.38	-2.00
	3	5.66	6.15	-0.48	-0.18	3.71	9.93	-6.22	-2.98	-2.77	6.84	-6.06	-3.16
	4	6.22	5.20	1.02	-1.40	3.35	10.65	-7.30	-2.71	-0.25	6.19	-6.44	-3.00
	5	7.08	8.13	-1.05	0.19	2.97	11.06	-8.08	-2.74	-2.01	6.89	-8.91	-2.09
	mean	6.99	5.75	1.24	-0.95	3.40	10.22	-6.82	-2.82	-0.42	6.70	-6.41	-2.37
Over all mean		7.12	6.19	0.57	-1.19	2.07	9.30	-7.20	-2.18	-1.07	6.87	-7.74	-2.55

Narmada valley showed positive ΔG_r values for K-Ca and K-Na exchange, which indicated that these soils had ready availability of K over Ca and Na⁴. Negative values for K-Ca exchange implied a strong preference of K⁺ relative to Ca²⁺ ions⁵. In general, ΔG_r values for Na-Ca and Ca-Mg exchange in Entisols of Location-1 were seen positive which ranged from -1.09 to 2.48 and -0.81 to 1.69 kJ mol⁻¹, respectively. Positive values of ΔG_r for Na-Ca exchange indicated that Entisols of Surguja district prefer Ca²⁺ and release Na⁺ ions, whereas these values for Ca-Mg exchange indicated that the given soils prefer Mg²⁺ and release Ca²⁺ in soil solution. In Location-2, ΔG_r values for Na-Ca exchange were generally positive which indicated ready availability of Na⁺ over Ca²⁺ ions, whereas these values for Ca-Mg exchange were negative, ranging from -2.62 and 0.79 kJ mol⁻¹. This suggested that these soils release more Mg²⁺ ion in soil solution.

The ΔG_r values for Na-Ca and Ca-Mg exchange in Inceptisols of both the locations were found negative and ranged from 0.00 to -11.76 and -0.67 to -2.68 kJ mol⁻¹, respectively, in Location-1, whereas in Location-2 these values ranged from -6.14 to -9.49 and -0.18 to -3.40 kJ mol⁻¹, respectively. The negative magnitudes of ΔG_r indicate that these soils release more Ca²⁺ compared to Na⁺ considering free bonding energy for Na-Ca exchange, whereas for Ca-Mg exchange these soils prefer Mg²⁺ on exchange site⁶, thereby releasing Ca²⁺ in soil solution. Similarly, negative values for ΔG_r in Alfisols of both the locations, observed for Na-Ca and Ca-Mg exchange, indicated release of Ca²⁺, considering ΔG_r for Na-Ca exchange and release of Mg²⁺, considering ΔG_r for Ca-Mg exchange. Therefore, the Alfisols, in particular, the study areas would pose more water-logging problem if irrigated injudiciously, since Mg is known to have similar effect like Na⁷.

The Alfisols of both the study areas showed negative ΔG_r values for K-Ca exchange and positive values for K-Na exchange (Table 1). The negative values of ΔG_r for K-Ca indicated preference for K⁺ ion, thereby releasing Ca²⁺ ions in the Alfisols of the study area, whereas positive values of ΔG_r for K-Na exchange showed ready availability of K and preference of Na on the exchange site. Thus, it is apparent that the Alfisols under study areas were found to possess higher K releasing power.

From the preceding discussion, it is concluded that the Entisols, Inceptisols and Alfisols of the study area in the Central India had ready availability of K and Ca, and that these soils will not pose any Na hazards under management strategy for sustainable agricultural production.

Experimental

An Elico LI 612 pH analyzer, an CM 180 electrical conductivity bridge and a Systronics 128 flame photometer were used for the analysis of pH, electrical conductivity, Na and K content of the given soils, respectively. All reagents and chemicals used were of A.R. grade.

General properties of the soils : The study area selected was the North-Eastern region of Madhya Pradesh under Surguja and Raigarh districts. Geographically this area is situated between 21°15' to 23°15' N latitude and 82°55' to 84°20' E longitude and 22°38' to 23°15' N latitude and 82°32' to 84°24' E longitude in the Surguja and Raigarh districts, respectively. To investigate the free bonding energy for exchange of the cations of the soils of study areas, 120 surface soil samples (0–20 cm) were collected in bulk, blockwise from intensive cultivated areas from two different locations, representing three soil orders, viz. Entisols, Inceptisols and Alfisols of Eastern Madhya Pradesh in the districts of Surguja and Raigarh, respectively. The soils collected had wide areal extent in the study area. The soil samples collected were air-dried and processed to pass through a 2-mm sieve and stored in a cool place. Physico-chemical properties of the soils, viz. soil texture, pH, EC, organic carbon, calcium carbonate, water-soluble and exchangeable cations, viz. Ca²⁺, Mg²⁺, Na⁺ and K⁺ were analyzed using the standard procedures⁸. Ca²⁺ and Mg²⁺ contents of the given soils were determined by Versenate titration (using EDTA), and water-soluble and exchangeable Na⁺ and K⁺ were analyzed flame-photometrically.

Free bonding energy : The mean free bonding energy (ΔG_r) for K-Ca, K-Na, Na-Ca and Ca-Mg exchange were calculated⁹. In brief, selectivity number for this exchange was calculated from the ratio (taking example for K⁺ and Ca²⁺ ions) given below :

$$S_{K-Ca} = (K_{se}/K_{ext})/(Ca_{se}/Ca_{ext})$$

where S_{K-Ca} stands for selectivity number for K-Ca exchange, 'se' for quantity of the cation concerned in saturation extract (me/liter) and 'ext' for extractable cation (me/100 g). The selectivity number, S_{K-Ca} , was used in the following equation to obtain the corresponding ΔG_r values by the following equation :

$$\Delta G_r = RT \ln S_{K-Ca}$$

where R is the universal gas constant (8.314 J mol⁻¹K⁻¹), T the absolute temperature (K).

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